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Pathways for Value Chains to Strengthen Sustainable Development in Mountain Regions: A European Cross-Case Analysis Based on Stakeholders' Perceptions

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ABSTRACT

Mountain areas are hotspots of high natural and cultural value, but they face sustainability challenges. This research offers a quantitative cross-case analysis of 21 case studies from mountain regions across 14 European countries, examining how local stakeholders perceive the contribution of mountain value chains to sustainable development. Using a cocreation process, seven objectives were defined and ranked via best–worst scaling choice experiments. A latent class model revealed four distinct development pathways: *Ecological prioritisation*, focusing on resilience and local assets; *Social prioritisation*, emphasising well-being, cooperation, and human capital; *Cooperative sustainability*, valuing cooperation and sustainable use of local assets; and *Balanced sustainability*, assigning similar importance to all the objectives. For all pathways, inclusiveness was rated as the least important objective. These results demonstrate that stakeholder priorities vary significantly, suggesting that ‘one-size-fits-all’ policies are ineffective. Our findings support the design of context-specific governance mechanisms to enhance the sustainability of European mountain regions through more targeted and stakeholder-aligned interventions.

1 | Introduction

Mountains are socioecological systems (SES) in which landscapes, livelihood opportunities and ecosystem services arise from complex interactions among local ecosystems, economic activities and cultural factors (Hunt et al. 2018; Klein et al. 2019). These interactions shape complex adaptive systems (Berkes and Folke 1998) that provide essential public goods and services. Mountains cover 36% of the land area in Europe and are home to 17% of the population, spanning numerous national borders and supporting a diverse array of ecosystems and land uses (Drexler et al. 2016; Price et al. 2004). Mountain ranges have been described as Europe’s ‘undervalued ecological backbone’, supplying essential ecosystem services that are rarely sufficiently compensated by markets or policy incentives. Moreover, they yield a variety of goods with benefits that serve not only

local communities but also hold social, economic and environmental importance for the continent as a whole (European Environmental Agency 2010). However, in recent decades, mountain ecosystems have become increasingly vulnerable to pressures such as climate change, demographic decline, and limited economic competitiveness (González-Moreno et al. 2025). This has sparked renewed interest in strategies based on improving mountain value chains to enhance long-term sustainability and resilience (European Commission 2025), in line with the European Commission’s Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas, which aims to establish resilient and vibrant rural regions by 2040 (European Commission 2021).

Value chains are defined as the full range of tasks that firms and actors undertake to bring a product from conception to end use, encompassing activities that generate value at different

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stages—production, processing, marketing, distribution, and consumption (Crescenzi and Harman 2023). Mountain value chains are those in which at least one of the initial stages of the value chain is developed in mountain areas. In the current context of globalisation and increasing competitiveness, mountain value chains face specific challenges, such as difficulties in reaching economies of scale and reducing production costs, obstacles to attracting or retaining specialised workers, poor infrastructure and access to digital opportunities and limited recognition and compensation, if any, for the public goods and ecosystem services they provide (Gloersen et al. 2016). Mountain value chains can promote the sustainable management of mountain areas by creating economic, social, and environmental value through the mobilisation of actors and endogenous resources, as well as fostering linkages across territorial and sectoral boundaries (Blackstock et al. 2025).

Sustainable development is traditionally defined in terms of the Brundtland Report or more recently, in terms of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations 2015). It refers to the capacity to meet present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (WCED 1987). Central to the concept of sustainable development is the need to adopt a holistic approach that addresses social, economic and ecological objectives, embraces a long-term perspective in development planning, considers multiple geographic scales, especially the local level and utilises governance mechanisms that promote stakeholder participation (Holden et al. 2014; Wheeler 2013), including marginalised people (Shortall 2008). In this respect, there is a growing focus on the role of value chains in strengthening the sustainable development of rural communities (Minh and Osei-Amponsah 2021), especially in challenging contexts such as mountain areas (Gloersen et al. 2016; European Commission 2025).

The sustainability of rural SES is shaped by factors such as resilience (the capacity to absorb disturbances and adapt), governance (polycentric, participatory and adaptive institutions) (Cash et al. 2006), social learning, diversity, and the ability to manage trade-offs between social, ecological and economic goals (Delgado-Serrano 2017; Fischer et al. 2015; Gain et al. 2020). All of these elements also influence how the rural value chains are shaped and built and how these chains contribute in return to the development of a region (Blackstock et al. 2025). However, the measurement and quantification of sustainability entail significant challenges due to conceptual disciplinary ambiguities, the existence of competing frameworks in the literature, as well as methodological issues in the operationalisation of the concepts (Diaz-Balteiro et al. 2017; Mura et al. 2018). Most of these frameworks underscore the importance of participatory approaches to incorporating the views and knowledge of local actors, thereby capturing the diverse range of needs and priorities (Hermans et al. 2011; Loconto and Hatanaka 2018; Moallemi et al. 2020). Furthermore, engaging local actors in the sustainability assessment of SES enables them to learn about the system's dynamics, including uncertainties arising from the drivers of change that shape its resilience and vulnerability. Such knowledge could inform effective mechanisms for adapting

to change and managing uncertainty (Berkes et al. 2000) and allow stakeholders to view the system as a whole, thereby reducing the challenges and unintended consequences associated with a focus on a single part of the system or a single process. This is particularly crucial for complex problems, such as analysing how rural value chains can contribute to rural sustainability (Vogel et al. 2020).

The literature analysing local stakeholders' perspectives on the role of value chains in the sustainable development of rural and mountain areas is limited and varies in its approach. Focusing on three rural areas in southeastern Italy, Lopolito et al. (2015) analyse local stakeholders' perceptions of development strategies for establishing new bio-based activities using a fuzzy cognitive mapping approach. They find that specific strategies are preferred depending on the area and identify three distinct strategies related to the production system (including enhancing economies of scale, resource availability, subsidies etc.), marketing and environmental regulation and the development of an innovation ecosystem (e.g., fostering private cooperation and public involvement). Vogel et al. (2020) analyse local stakeholders' perceptions of the performance of transition pathways towards sustainability in Cameroon's cocoa value chain, mainly using a qualitative approach and conducting focus groups to discuss a set of economic, social and environmental indicators. They find that stakeholders prefer a sustainability pathway based on certification standards, as it largely outperforms the other pathways considered (state-, private- and supply-driven) in those indicators. Finizola e Silva et al. (2024) assess stakeholders' perspectives on sustainable food value chains using Q-methodology in a case study of two Kenyan counties, identifying different perspectives on what a sustainable food value chain should look like. These perspectives are related to economic productivity, food security, environmental prioritisation and transformative knowledge.

Focusing on mountain areas, studies assessing sustainability through stakeholder knowledge are often based on specific case studies and tend to concentrate on certain functions and dimensions of sustainability or policy scenarios. Examples of stakeholder-based case studies of sustainability in mountain areas include protected areas in the Spanish Pyrenees (Zango-Palau et al. 2024; Jolivet et al. 2026), northern Greece (Tzanopoulos et al. 2011), eastern Slovakia (Bezáková and Bezák 2022), as well as mountainous districts in the western Indian Himalayas (Choudhary et al. 2013) and northern Pakistan (Baig et al. 2021). A few case studies examine more than one region: for example, Muñoz-Ulecia et al. (2022) focus on the Italian Alps and the Spanish Pre-Pyrenees or Villanueva et al. (2015) examine specific cases in the Austrian Alps and southern Spain; while Soliva et al. (2008) and, more recently, Blackstock et al. (2025) undertake a multicase, stakeholder-based analysis.

A variety of methods are employed to analyse sustainability through stakeholders' knowledge. These include, on the one hand, qualitative approaches using focus groups or a small sample of stakeholders (Soliva et al. 2008; Tzanopoulos et al. 2011) and descriptive variables (Choudhary et al. 2013; Baig et al. 2021; Bezáková and Bezák 2022) or a mix of both

(Blackstock et al. 2025) and, on the other hand, more quantitative approaches that rely on stated preference methods (Muñoz-Ulecia et al. 2022), multicriteria analysis (Villanueva et al. 2015) and mixed methods (e.g., structural equation modelling and network analysis, in the case of Zango-Palau et al. 2024). Some studies focus on the provision of environmental services (Soliva et al. 2008; Villanueva et al. 2015; Muñoz-Ulecia et al. 2022) and use scenario analysis (e.g., comparing business as usual, liberalisation and more pro-environmental scenarios by means of ‘what if’ frameworks) (Soliva et al. 2008; Tzanopoulos et al. 2011; Bezáková and Bezák 2022), though analyses of mountain value chains are in the minority (Choudhary et al. 2013; Baig et al. 2021; Blackstock et al. 2025). Blackstock et al. (2025) set a precedent for cross-case analyses of mountain sustainability through the value chain lens, yet there is still no stakeholder-based study that examines the contribution of mountain value chains to sustainable development using a multi-case, quantitative approach.

The present study attempts to fill that gap by quantitatively assessing stakeholders’ perceptions of how these value chains contribute to the sustainable development of mountain regions. To that end, a conceptual framework cocreated by mountain experts and qualified stakeholders as part of an H2020 project was applied using an online survey comprising a best–worst-scaling choice experiment approach administered to a sample of qualified local stakeholders from a wide range of European mountain value chains. This research aims to contribute new empirical evidence to existing knowledge by combining a novel value-chain-oriented framework, local stakeholder knowledge and a stated-preference quantitative methodology for a cross-case and cross-country analysis of different mountain areas. This is particularly timely given the increasing policy interest in European mountain value chains (European Commission 2025).

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Definition of Objectives

The starting point for our study is the conceptual framework proposed by Moretti et al. (2023), which combines the Ostrom SES framework (Ostrom 2009) with value chain analysis to identify the outcomes of these value chains in mountain areas. The framework analyses how the social practices implemented by various actors in a value chain mobilise territorial resources and connect actors both internally and beyond territorial boundaries and economic sectors, yielding different results that influence the sustainability and resilience of mountain SES. In this study, we tested the framework across 23 value chains in as many mountain regions across 16 European countries, involving more than 700 stakeholders (see Appendix A, which outlines the value chains considered in the study—Table A1—and shows their geographical distribution—Figure A1). Across all mountain regions, multiactor platforms were established to form a community of practice in each region, gathering stakeholders from diverse groups, including producers, local businesses organisations, institutions, associations, NGOs, citizens, government bodies, municipalities and external experts. Using participatory and qualitative approaches organised around workshops and

focus groups to draw out stakeholders’ opinions, we analysed the vulnerability of mountain value chains to environmental and social drivers (González-Moreno et al. 2025). The economic, environmental and social values that the value chains bring to the mountain areas have been analysed by Blackstock et al. (2025) and a foresight analysis of the potential of these value chains to contribute to resilient and sustainable futures is provided in Smith et al. (2026).

As part of these analyses, stakeholders and project researchers collaboratively established a set of objectives that reflect how value chains can contribute to the sustainable development of mountain areas. Based on that work, Grando et al. (2024) expanded the initial framework by incorporating the system’s outcomes stemming from mountain value chains. Specifically, these outcomes comprise the following objectives identified by stakeholders, on which the current analysis is built (see Figure 1): Cooperation (O1), Human capital (O2), Sustainable use of local assets (O3), Inclusiveness (O4), Adaptive capacity (O5), Ecological resilience (O6) and Attractiveness & wellbeing (O7) (see Grando et al. 2024, for an in-depth explanation of the framework).

Figure 2 describes the objectives considered in the analysis, which represent the expected outcomes that local value-chain practices can deliver. They were formulated using a normative approach (Cialdini et al. 1991), which is based on values about what *ought to be* rather than merely describing what *is* and they account for the elements value chains should deliver to enhance the sustainability of the mountain SES. These objectives are in addition to private economic performance (profitability), which is presumed to be an intrinsic goal of value chains. To facilitate the analysis, the objectives were limited in number, making cross-comparison simpler and ensuring relevance across multiple value chains and countries. They were also written in lay terms, avoiding scientific jargon, to make them easier for stakeholders to understand. They were validated by more than 100 stakeholders representing the 23 mountain areas who attended a workshop in Budapest in 2023.

The objectives reflect the idea that value chains can support the sustainable development of mountain regions by strengthening the social, environmental, and economic foundations of these vulnerable areas. For instance, cooperation enables producers and local actors overcome fragmentation and empower local networks, while investment in human capital ensures that specialised knowledge and skills are available to fuel innovation and sustain production (King et al. 2019). In this respect, the long-term viability of mountain areas may depend on how responsibly value chains use SES resources and preserve the ecosystems that support them. In addition, inclusiveness can foster the participation of women, youth and newcomers, which is crucial in areas facing demographic decline. At the same time, building adaptive capacity enhances the ability of value chains to cope with climate change, market fluctuations and other shocks, while ecological resilience ensures that local environments can face and recover from shocks and continue to provide essential services (Holling 1973). Finally, value chains bolster the attractiveness and wellbeing of mountain areas by supporting livelihoods, maintaining cultural landscapes and making these regions more appealing places

FIGURE 1 | The conceptual framework used for our analysis, presenting the seven sustainability objectives associated with mountain value chains at the bottom of the dashed box. *Source:* Grando et al. (2024).

to live and work. Together, these objectives delineate how functioning value chains can become powerful drivers of sustainable mountain development.

2.2 | Data Collection

We collected stakeholders' opinions on the relative salience of these seven objectives for the sustainability of mountain SES using a structured online questionnaire administered through the European Union survey platform. The online questionnaire was made available in the stakeholders' mother tongue¹ and widely disseminated via the project's Virtual Research Environment (a web-based, community-oriented workspace hosted by D4Science where project members interacted, stored and managed data, ran analyses, shared tools and collaborated seamlessly) and, crucially, through partners working with their Multi-Actor Platforms. The European Commission approved the ethical considerations related to informed consent in participatory research and data management in July 2022, as part of the project's ethical guidelines. Partners identified and contacted a panel of 5–10 knowledgeable stakeholders per country, selecting people with a comprehensive understanding of local value

chains and their territorial effects. This purposive sampling approach was aimed at assembling respondents from diverse professional backgrounds—agriculture, food processing, forestry, tourism, administration and policy, nature conservation, among others—to enable comparison across expertise, priorities and viewpoints. Of 133 invitees from the 16 countries involved in the project, more than 100 provided valid responses, spanning different mountain regions in most of the countries involved in the project. The fieldwork ran from 18 October to 20 December 2023. The survey tool allowed participants to choose their preferred language, imposed no time limit and did not require them to answer questions in a fixed order.

2.3 | Best–Worst Scaling Implementation

To uncover the trade-offs that stakeholders make among the seven objectives considered, we implemented a best–worst scaling discrete choice experiment exercise. To complete this exercise, respondents repeatedly selected the most and least important items from small sets; the observed best and worst frequencies reveal each item's standing on the latent importance continuum (Marley and Louviere 2005; Flynn and Marley 2012).

FIGURE 2 | Objectives considered for the analysis: possible contributions of mountain value chains to the sustainable development of mountain areas.

The BWS approach, widely employed for preference elicitation in health economics, environmental policy and consumer research (e.g., Lancsar et al. 2007; Glenk et al. 2014; Villanueva et al. 2025), is well suited to our study because it is easy to comprehend, sharpens trade-off measurement, mitigates common rating biases and scales efficiently to multiple items (Lusk and Briggeman 2009; Lancsar et al. 2013).

We used a case 1 BWS (the object case, see Flynn and Marley 2012). Regarding the experimental design by which items (objectives for the mountain value chains to enhance the sustainable development of mountain areas) were distributed among best-worst choice tasks, we opted for a balanced incomplete block design (BIBD) with three items per task in a sequence of seven tasks. A BIBD ensures constant occurrence and co-occurrences of items, minimising unintended potential biases stemming from the presentation of items among the different choice tasks (Flynn and Marley 2012). For each task, respondents indicated which objective was the most and least important for the development of the mountain areas (Figure 3), explicitly taking into account implementation effort and potential co-benefits for actors in their current situation. This sequential choice process yielded a ranking of relative importance across all seven objectives.

In addition to the BWS exercise, the questionnaire included questions about the stakeholders' demographic and professional characteristics, their country and the mountain value chain with which they were involved. The questionnaire also included

open-ended prompts regarding existing practices/relationships that advance the chosen objectives, the support needed (e.g., policies, programmes or actors) and current obstacles to better performance. An English version of the questionnaire is provided as [Supporting Information](#).

2.4 | Modelling

The econometric analysis of BWS responses is grounded in random utility theory adapted for best-worst tasks (Flynn and Marley 2012). As the present analysis aims to disentangle the heterogeneity in stakeholders' perceptions of the contribution of mountain value chains to the sustainable development of mountain areas, a latent class model (LCM) was used. This modelling approach allows preferences to vary across a number of discrete latent classes, with homogeneous preferences within each class (Boxall and Adamowicz 2002). Individuals can then be grouped according to their preferences, which in previous studies has proved useful for identifying heterogeneous environmental benefits (e.g., Boxall and Adamowicz 2002), creating marketing strategies that target different groups of consumers (e.g., Villanueva et al. 2025) or better targeting land-use policies (e.g., Niskanen et al. 2021), among other outcomes. In this study, it is especially useful for identifying diverse pathways through which mountain value chains can contribute to the sustainable development of mountain areas. In LCMs, the number of classes is set by the analyst. In this study, it was set on the basis

11 Choice Card 5

11.1 In the table below, between the three objectives proposed select the most important and the least important.

	Adaptive capacity Actors are aware of their role and responsibility to support the adaptation and mitigation of socio-economic threats, such as depopulation, isolation, inflation, etc. They take appropriate action and consideration of these threats in strategic decisions.	Ecological resilience Actors are aware of their role and responsibility in helping to adapt to and mitigate environmental threats such as climate change, water scarcity, and biodiversity changes. They take appropriate actions and considerations of these threats into account when making strategic decisions.	Cooperation Actors engage in formal and informal relationships in the value chain, fostering fruitful collaboration. This collaboration also leads to sharing benefits fairly among all involved parties throughout the production, processing, and distribution phases.
The most important	●	●	●
The least important	●	●	●

FIGURE 3 | An example of a best–worst scaling choice card.

of information criteria alongside considerations of parsimony and interpretability (Swait 1994). Specifically, a four-class solution was selected as the best compromise between model fit and parsimony, based on the diminishing returns exhibited by the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) and the clarity it affords for drawing policy-relevant insights. The final specification also included covariates related to the mountain value chain to which the stakeholder is linked, with the aim of providing further information on the determinants of class membership. To facilitate interpretation, we transformed the estimated model coefficients into ratio-scaled ‘impact scores’ (Sawtooth 2013). More in-depth information on the econometric specification is provided in Appendix B and information on model fit across different specifications in Appendix D.

3 | Results

The final sample comprised 108 stakeholders across 14 European countries (Austria, Czechia, France, Greece, Hungary, Italy, North Macedonia, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey).² Surveyed stakeholders were evenly distributed across various sectors, including the primary sector (agriculture and forestry), secondary sector (processing and manufacturing, energy etc.), tertiary sector (tourism and gastronomy, consulting services, sports and leisure activities etc.) and the public sector (administration and policy, natural parks and conservation, research, education etc.). Other relevant characteristics of the sample are as follows: 27% of respondents fell within the 25–40 age range, while the majority (69%) were between 40 and 65 years old; 38% were women and 93% held a

university degree. Each country contributed between 5 and 12 completed questionnaires, except for Spain (16) and Portugal (4). Appendix C shows descriptive information about the sample (Table C1) and the sectors (Figure C1) to which the surveyed stakeholders were attached.

The final model comprised a four-class LCM, which presented high goodness of fit. Solutions with a greater number of classes presented meagre improvements in model fit compared to this one, but with a notable increase in the number of parameters (Appendix D, Table D2, includes model fit statistics for different specifications, demonstrating the suitability of the four-class solution). To explore heterogeneity in more depth, we included covariates to explain class membership. Table 1 presents the estimates from the final four-class LCM, including the significant covariates for class membership. Appendix D reports alternative specifications such as the multinomial logit baseline and the four-class LCM without covariates (Table D3), along with descriptive statistics for the best and worst choices (Table D1). Both of them turned out to be highly significant, with the latter displaying a very similar class structure as compared to the four-class LCM with covariates, reinforcing the robustness of our results. All the coefficients related to objectives were statistically significant at the 1% level, underscoring the robustness of the model. The fact that all these coefficients are positive implies a significant preference for any of the objectives considered over O4-Inclusiveness (used as reference). A significant scale coefficient for worst choices (least important) was found, suggesting greater uncertainty in these choices compared to the best choices (most important). This mirrors previous evidence in other valuation contexts (e.g., Villanueva et al. 2025).

TABLE 1 | Statistical results for our four-class latent class logit model (LCM) of best–worst choices, including covariates of class membership (reference = O4-Inclusiveness).

	Class 1		Class 2		Class 3		Class 4	
	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE
Membership probability	0.166		0.263		0.215		0.356	
Main parameters								
O1-Cooperation	5.777***	1.515	2.686***	0.608	5.714***	0.878	1.698***	0.387
O2-Human capital	6.152***	1.531	2.562***	0.612	3.501***	0.844	1.778***	0.389
O3-Sustainable use of local assets	7.210***	1.545	1.606***	0.494	4.670***	0.874	2.593***	0.402
O5-Adaptive capacity	3.973***	1.369	2.184***	0.598	3.585***	0.780	2.429***	0.418
O6-Ecological resilience	8.488***	1.602	1.610***	0.496	2.784***	0.779	2.857***	0.411
O7-Attractiveness & wellbeing	6.155***	1.520	3.578***	0.552	2.978***	0.793	2.193***	0.416
Class specific constant	1.561	1.278	2.321*	1.284	0.859***	1.316	−4.740***	2.990
Covariates								
Mediterranean	1.410*	0.840	1.531*	0.870	−0.387	0.833	−2.554**	1.096
PDO	3.321**	1.542	−5.091	3.619	1.495	1.389	0.275	1.402
Organic	2.234	2.457	3.756*	2.008	0.177	1.823	−6.166	4.423
Animalp	−7.396*	3.827	−1.558	1.828	1.124	1.769	7.830**	3.278
Permcrops	−3.504**	1.469	−2.664*	1.369	−1.206	1.524	7.375**	3.164
CultureHi	−1.148*	0.675	0.325	0.652	0.109	0.630	0.714	0.751
DiversifiHi	0.281	0.792	−1.704**	0.735	0.333	0.773	1.090	0.727
Scale factor worst responses	−0.468**	0.157						
Goodness of fit								
LL	−1079.12							
AIC/N	0.995							
Observations (individuals)	2268 (108)							

Note: ***, **, * denote significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively.

Figure 4 illustrates the relative importance of each objective for achieving sustainability through value chains in mountain regions, calculated from the LCM coefficients listed in Table 1. As seen in Figure 4 (see the right-hand side, 'All'), the most important objectives are O3-Sustainable use of local assets, O1-Cooperation, O7-Attractiveness & wellbeing and O6-Ecological resilience (in that order), each scoring between 17% and 18% in relative importance. Considering that the total contribution of all seven objectives sums up to 100%, these figures can be interpreted as indicating that meeting each of these objectives would contribute a 17%–18% share to the development of the mountain regions. In contrast, O4-Inclusiveness is clearly the lowest-ranked objective, scoring just 1.7% (meaning that meeting this objective would make only a very minor contribution to the development of these regions compared to the other objectives). O2-Human capital and O5-Adaptive capacity score 14.4% and 13.7% in relative importance, respectively. However, the results show a high level of heterogeneity, as can be observed in the results displayed per class in Figure 4.

Class 1 (17% of the membership probability) appears to prioritise O6-Ecological resilience and O3-Sustainable use of local assets, which together score more than 50% in terms of their relative importance for the development of mountain areas. Accordingly, we name this class *C1-Ecological priorities*. Members of Class 1 are more likely to be from Mediterranean countries (variable Mediterranean) and involved in value chains associated with a protected designation of origin (variable PDO). Conversely, stakeholders attached to permanent crop or livestock-based value chains (variables Permcrops and Animalp) or those who perceive that their value chain strongly contributes to local culture/education (CultureHi) have a lower probability of belonging to this class.

Class 2 (26% of the membership probability) exhibits a strong preference for O7-Attractiveness & wellbeing, as well as for O1-Cooperation and O2-Human capital. Together, these objectives account for almost two-thirds of the importance in this profile, indicating a focus on social objectives. We thus name it *C2-Social priorities*. Belonging to this class is positively related to

FIGURE 4 | Barplots of the relative importance scores of each objective (O1–O7), grouped by the classes resulting from our analysis (Classes 1–4, as well as altogether).

Mediterranean value chains and cases where the value chain relies on organic production (variable Organic). As with C1-Ecological priorities, belonging to C2-Social priorities is negatively associated with permanent cropping systems (Permcrops) and the variable DiversifiHi, meaning that the stakeholder perceives that the value chain to which s/he is attached strongly impacts the diversification of income sources.

In Class 3 (22% of the membership probability), O1-Cooperation (a social objective) and O3-Sustainable use of local assets (an environmental objective) predominate, together totalling 54% of the relative importance. This class thus represents a hybrid social–environmental pathway and is labelled *C3-Cooperative sustainability*. Notably, none of the examined covariates significantly predict membership in Class 3, implying that this group is broadly distributed without a clear demographic or regional pattern. Its intermediate characteristics suggest it may represent a middle-ground perspective on value chain development.

Class 4 is the largest class (36% of the membership probability) and is characterised by a more homogeneous distribution of importance across all objectives. This is illustrated by the highest minimum and the lowest maximum objective-specific importance scoring among classes (3%—score for O4-Inclusiveness and 22%—score for O6-Ecological resilience, respectively). In fact, six out of seven objectives show importance scoring higher than 10%, meaning there is no clear pattern of dominance by a single objective. As a result, we name this class *C4-Balanced sustainability*. The probability of belonging to this class is in marked opposition to Class 1 membership; it shows a negative relationship with Mediterranean and a positive relationship with Animalp and Permcrops.

4 | Discussion

The analysis emphasises how local stakeholders interpret the role of mountain value chains in the sustainable development of

European mountain areas. The results for the general ranking of objectives clearly indicate that objective O4-Inclusiveness contributes the least to sustainable development. Each of the other objectives contributes between 14% and 18% to sustainability, with the four highest-scoring objectives (O3-Sustainable use of local assets, O1-Cooperation, O7-Attractiveness & wellbeing and O6-Ecological resilience) accounting for over 70% of the total contribution of these seven objectives. It is worth noting that mountain value chains often involve only the production stage and, less commonly, the processing stage, as lowlands are preferred for the latter due to better facilities and infrastructure. Consumption is sometimes local, especially in value chains strongly linked to tourism and local food customs (Blackstock et al. 2025). Consequently, the results highlight the perceived importance of natural resources as key inputs in the operation of the value chains and emphasise the significance of these value chains in supporting livelihoods, environmental performance and community life in these regions.

In this context, O3-Sustainable use of local assets and O6-Ecological resilience clearly demonstrate the embeddedness of mountain value chains within territorial capital and local assets at the production stage. The emphasis on O6-Ecological resilience may suggest that participants are aware of environmental threats, such as resource scarcity and biodiversity loss, which could jeopardise the continuity of value chains (Zango-Palau et al. 2024; González-Moreno et al. 2025) and highlight the urgent need for value chains to implement strategic adaptation and mitigation actions (Brunner and Grêt-Regamey 2016; McDowell et al. 2019; Baig et al. 2021). The ranking of O1-Cooperation underscores the understanding of value chains as networks of actors that, through both formal and informal relationships, generate value when they collaborate while also recognising that cooperation and collaboration are essential to strengthening the value chains and realising benefits at various stages (Nyaga et al. 2010; Ricciotti 2020). The high priority assigned to O7-Attractiveness & wellbeing may reflect concerns among local stakeholders about another major threat: the depopulation and

abandonment of remote rural areas (Bezáková and Bezák 2022). In this respect, value chains are critical for creating jobs and income that attract and retain residents, thereby improving their wellbeing (Moretti et al. 2023). Depopulation and a lack of generational renewal were identified by Zagata et al. (2023) as relevant in most of the value chains analysed; exceptions include Trento mountain wines in Italy, where the diversification of activities made these areas more attractive. The gradual decline in the quality and availability of services related to rural inhabitants' wellbeing restricts the ability of value chains to support sustainable development (Gloersen et al. 2016).

Two more results from the overall ranking of objectives are worth discussing. The first relates to O2-Human capital, which, while receiving a lower average score, shows the narrowest scoring range (12%–18%) and the highest minimum scoring across categories. This suggests that, regardless of the pathway prioritised in value chain contribution to sustainability, this objective should not be ignored. Value chain performance depends on the practices of the actors involved (Moretti et al. 2023); hence, human capital is always a key asset for development. Second, the low score for O4-Inclusiveness can be interpreted in two ways: either participants perceive no major exclusion issues in the analysed value chains or they see limited potential for greater inclusiveness in the production stage, particularly regarding women, young people, non-locals or disabled individuals, due to the remoteness, physically demanding work and traditionally male-dominated roles in this stage. Previous findings highlighting sustainability conflicts among women and young people in mountain areas would support the latter interpretation (Fernández-Giménez et al. 2022). This finding clearly calls for further investigation of the role of inclusiveness in mountain value chains.

The results also demonstrate that there are different possible pathways for the sustainable development of European mountain areas and that a one-size-fits-all approach will not suit the diversity of mountain regions and value chains analysed. In particular, we identified four distinct pathway classes. Two of those (C1-Ecological priorities and C3-Cooperative sustainability) have more uneven priorities, where most of the importance is assigned to just two objectives and two have more balanced priorities (especially C4-Balanced sustainability and, to some extent, C2-Social priorities, with the latter leaning more towards social and human aspects). While previous studies have highlighted the diversity of stakeholders' views on sustainability pathways in case studies of specific mountains (e.g., Jolivet et al. 2026), this is the first study to show common pathways across a large number of different mountain areas. In addition, the analysis provides useful information about the probability of supporting each pathway, as it is significantly related to certain characteristics of the mountain value chain to which the stakeholder is attached; mainly features related to location, production type, certification and the activity's impact on cultural services and diversification.

The preferred pathway is C4-Balanced sustainability, where 36% of respondents envision a milieu in which environmental and social aspects cannot be separated, assigning a balanced role to the value chains in promoting sustainable development. Bezáková and Bezák (2022), Tzanopoulos et al. (2011) and Jolivet

et al. (2026) also found a preference for more balanced sustainability scenarios in mountain areas. This pathway is more common in value chains associated with animal-based products (cheese, meat) and permanent crops (vineyards, olive and carob groves). Both types of value chain require diverse specialised labour (i.e., technical services such as vets or quality controllers). Additionally, environmental aspects also play an important role in the performance of these value chains. In that respect, the significant added value of environmental services channelled through animal-based mountain value chains has been previously pointed out by Villanueva et al. (2021) for Iberian ham and Esgalhado et al. (2024) for high pasture cheese.

The second and third prioritised pathways (C2-Social priorities, accounting for 26% of participants and C3-Cooperative sustainability, preferred by 22%) place greater emphasis on objectives related to social aspects and the significance of people. These respondents perceive that value chains hold substantial power to enhance and revitalise mountain areas, especially by providing high-quality jobs and stable income. However, a strong focus on education and upskilling is necessary to tackle challenges and adapt to socio-economic and environmental threats (Coopmans et al. 2021). The C2 pathway was mainly linked to Mediterranean value chains and organic production systems. In many of these chains, we observed stronger alliances among producers—for instance, through cooperatives, certification schemes or associations—along with an increased need for collaborative practices and knowledge-sharing—for example, in developing phytosanitary schedules or soil-conservation practices. These contexts also often include a neo-rural presence (Vizuete et al. 2024), which tends to be more open to building connections with other actors. In contrast, the analysis does not show conclusive information on the characteristics related to the C3 pathway, as no covariate showed a clear significant association with C3 membership, thus indicating that further research is needed to identify factors related to this sustainability pathway.

The C1-Ecological priorities pathway reflects the preferences of 17% of respondents for environment-related objectives (O3-Sustainable use of local assets, O6-Ecological resilience). The smaller group size indicates the prevailing view that more balanced approaches, such as those suggested by C4-Balanced sustainability, may be more beneficial. This pathway is preferred in Mediterranean mountain value chains and those linked to protected designations of origin. The former preference may be associated with the severe environmental threats Mediterranean mountain value chains face due to climate change (droughts, pests and diseases, fires) (Scotti et al. 2023; González-Moreno et al. 2025). The latter reflects the strict rules for the sustainable use of natural resources, often documented in the requirements of many protected designations of origin. In this regard, previous research has highlighted the role of these designations in conserving natural resources and valorising environmental services, with some studies focusing particularly on Mediterranean areas (Flinzberger et al. 2022).

Finally, it is important to acknowledge the main limitations of the study. The assessment examines how mountain value chains can contribute to the sustainable development of the areas where they are located, considering a variety of contributions (objectives), value chains and mountain areas. While the cross-case

analysis helps make the results more generalisable, the diversity of cases and objectives makes it more challenging to identify cause-and-effect relationships. Given the limited number of studies of this kind, this research could be viewed as an initial step towards more comprehensive evaluations. For example, future assessments could incorporate value-based approaches (i.e., analysing the costs and benefits associated with achieving specific goals), explore different targets linked to objectives, expand the framework to include explicit connections between relevant factors and value-chain contributions or examine the role of new digital technologies in ensuring the sustainable and inclusive development of mountain areas (Finger 2023; Granado-Díaz et al. 2024). Furthermore, engaging a greater number of local stakeholders and covering more sectors (e.g., including creative industries) would better capture the variance across areas. This would inform better policies for enhancing the role of mountain value chains in the sustainable development of mountain areas.

5 | Conclusions

This research offers a unique quantitative, multi-country cross-case analysis of local stakeholder perceptions regarding the contribution of mountain value chains to the sustainable development of European mountain SESs. The results show that stakeholders prioritise mountain value chains meeting sustainability objectives related to the sustainable use of local assets, cooperation, ecological resilience and the attractiveness & well-being of mountain areas, while attaching a significantly lower importance to inclusiveness and an intermediate importance to human capital and adaptive capacity. However, as our analysis demonstrates, the perceived importance of these objectives varies considerably across stakeholders, depending on the characteristics of the mountain value chain in which they are embedded. In particular, four sustainability pathways have been identified, suggesting that no single development model suits all mountain regions. These pathways are labelled as: *ecological priorities*, *social priorities*, *cooperative sustainability* and *balanced sustainability*. While *balanced sustainability* is the preferred pathway for the largest group of stakeholders, other pathways emphasise *social* or *ecological priorities* depending on the characteristics, pressures and governance arrangements of each value chain. It is worth noting that human capital is consistently valued in all four pathways, highlighting the essential role of people, skills and knowledge in influencing value-chain performance.

From a policy-making perspective, our findings can inform the development of effective mechanisms to address vulnerabilities and support long-term planning, based on stakeholder perceptions. They also underscore the need for context-specific strategies and policies that recognise the diversity of European mountain areas and types of value chains. To this end, the information provided here about the diverse sustainability pathways through which mountain value chains can contribute, along with the value chain- and mountain area-specific factors related to each pathway, can be particularly useful. Recognising the specific priorities of a particular mountain area can help policy-makers allocate resources and design interventions that better meet the needs of local stakeholders, thereby enhancing the success of sustainable development initiatives.

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Endnotes

¹The questionnaire was available in the following languages: Bulgarian, Czech, English, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Italian, Macedonian, Portuguese, Romanian, Serbian, Slovak, Spanish and Turkish.

²No data were collected for the Scottish (whisky) and Bulgarian (farming) cases due to a lengthy delay in the ethical approval for the former and disengagement from the project for the latter. Thus, the number of value chains eventually covered in the analysis was 21.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Data S1:** sd71059-sup-0001-Supinfo.pdf.

Appendix A

Description of Value Chains Considered in the Analysis

TABLE A1 | Value chains considered in the analysis (Blackstock et al. 2025).

#	Abbreviation	Value chain product (additional VC)	Mountain locality (and area km ²)	Mainland use system in locality	Main territorial capitals
1	Austrian lamb	Lamb (curd cheese)	Weiz Bergland (836)	Extensive open-range lowland meadows and highland pastures	Diverse economic institutions Communal pasture institutions Landscape mosaic
2	Bulgarian farming ^a	High nature value farming (none)	Western Stara Planina (1660)	Mosaic (semi-) natural system consisting of grassland and forest	Semi-natural meadows Rare plants and animals
3	Czech beef	Beef (tourism)	Strazny, Lenora, Horni Vltavice (125)	Extensive open rangeland	Cattle housing and meat processing units Knowledge and social capital Protected habitats
4	Corsican flour	Chestnut flour (none)	Bucugnà, Ghisoni and Nuceta (358)	High intensity forest (Agroforestry)	Orchards and processing infrastructure Knowledge and traditional buildings Rare plants and animals
5	French lamb	Spring lamb (sheep meat)	Drome Valley (378)	Extensive open pastures	Agricultural buildings, livestock diversity Communal pasture institutions Protected habitats, scenery
6	Cretan flour	Carob flour (animal feed)	Central Rethymno (394)	Agro-silvo-pastoral	Diverse economic institutions Traditions, community support Protected habitats, cultural heritage sites
7	Hungarian knowledge	Agro-ecological knowledge (tourism)	Barnag, Pecsely (32)	Mosaic land use system (crops, forestry)	Workforce, land values, equipment Knowledge/skills, cooperation Water, climate, landscape
8	Italian cheese	Spun paste cheese (beef, tourism)	Alto Molise (276)	Agro-silvo-pastoral system	Economic institutions Traditions, educated residents, voluntary associations Water, habitats, geology
9	Italian wine	Wine (grappa)	Trento (158)	Permanent cropland	Diverse economic institutions, winery infrastructure Knowledge, cooperation, heritage Water, climate, biodiversity
10	Italian flour	Chestnut flour (chestnut honey, beer)	Stazzema, Seravezza (120)	High intensity forest (Agroforestry)	Landscape character Traditions Water networks
11	Macedonian tourism	Rural tourism (none)	Berovo, Pehchevo (806)	Mosaic land use system (natural and planted forestry)	Economic growth Socio-cultural development Nature conservation

(Continues)

TABLE A1 | (Continued)

#	Abbreviation	Value chain product (additional VC)	Mountain locality (and area km ²)	Mainland use system in locality	Main territorial capitals
12	Portuguese cheese	Cheese (lamb, curd cheese)	Serra da Estrela (305)	Extensive open rangeland (highland and lowland pasture)	Local breeds, fodder Traditions and knowledge Landscape, climate
13	Portuguese wine	Wine (tourism, almonds, olive oil)	Vila Nova de Foz Coa (90)	Permanent cropland	Winery infrastructure, brand, diverse economic institutions Designated landscapes traditions and knowledge Biodiversity, climate, local varieties
14	Romanian ecotourism	Certified ecotourism (tourism)	Parts of Brasov County and Fundata Argeş county (846)	Mosaic landscape with forest and extensive semi-natural grassland	Traditions and heritage Landscape mosaic
15	Serbian lamb	Lamb (cheese, dried meat)	Sjenica (2541)	Extensive open rangeland/Mosaic cropland (extensive)	Labour force, cooperatives Traditions, knowledge Biodiversity, alpine forests
16	Slovakian honey	Bio-honey (pollen-based health products)	Polomka, Bacuch, Bravacovo (161)	Mosaic landscape with pastures, meadows and forest	Local consumers Traditions, knowledge, skills Landscape mosaic
17	Spanish olive oil	Organic olive oil (other organic products, e.g., almonds)	Carcabuey, Priego de Córdoba, Zuheros (410)	High intensity forest (Agroforestry)	Agricultural infrastructure, workforce, brands Tradition, community support Landscape mosaic, local varieties, biodiversity
18	Spanish ham	Iberian ham (non-PDO ham)	Villanueva de Córdoba, Pozoblanco, Cardena (1273)	Agro-silvo-pastoral system	Agricultural infrastructure, Knowledge, social capital, cooperation Biodiversity, climate, landscape mosaic
19	Spanish wine	Wine (almonds)	Ayerbe and Loarre (138)	Permanent cropland	Diverse economic institutions Traditions, heritage Protected habitats and local species
20	Swiss grain	Grain (beef, milk, manure)	Grisons (7104)	Permanent cropland	Diverse economic institutions Diverse populations, designated landscapes, tradition
21	Swiss cheese	Cheese (cheese)	Jura, Berne (753)	Extensive open rangeland	Agricultural infrastructure, Diverse economic institutions Skills, knowledge, reputation, networks Pastures, local breeds
22	Turkish tomatoes	Tomatoes (peppers, cucumbers)	Elmali (1433)	Intensive irrigated cropland	Workforce, agricultural infrastructure, diverse economic institutions Traditions, heritage Local vegetation
23	Scotch whisky ^a	Malt whisky (tourism)	West Moray, Badenoch & Strathspey (3414)	Extensive rangeland	Workforce Heritage, knowledge, relationships Water, scenery

^a Although a priori included in the analysis, no completed questionnaires were collected from these cases.

Source: Blackstock et al. (2025).

FIGURE A1 | Geographical distribution of the 23 mountain regions where the value chain case studies are located (see Table A1 for a brief description of each).

Appendix B

Econometric Specification

The econometric analysis of BWS responses is grounded in random utility theory adapted for best–worst tasks (Flynn and Marley 2012). Let the latent importance that stakeholder n associates with objective i in choice task t be decomposed into a systematic component and a stochastic term ($\epsilon_{ni,t}$) with the usual i.i.d. type-I extreme value assumption, implying constant error variance $\pi^2/6$ (Equation B1).

$$U_{ni,t} = V_{ni,t} + \epsilon_{ni,t} \quad (B1)$$

The deterministic component captures each objective's contribution to the latent utility scale for the sustainable development of mountain areas (Equation B2), where an indicator marks the availability of objective i in task t ($I_{ni,t}$) and the associated utility parameter (α_{ni}) represents its contribution according to stakeholder n .

$$V_{ni,t} = \alpha_{ni} I_{ni,t} \quad (B2)$$

The probability that objective i is chosen as 'best' (most important) in task t is given by a conditional logit (CL) model with a scale parameter μ normalised to one (Equation B3).

$$P_n(y_{\text{best}} = i | \alpha_n, t) = \frac{\exp(\mu V_{ni,t})}{\sum_{j=1}^J \exp(\mu V_{nj,t})} \quad (B3)$$

We model 'best' ($y_{\text{best}} = b$) and 'worst' (least important $y_{\text{worst}} = w$) choices jointly by assuming a sequential decision process—best first (t_1), then worst (t_2) from the remaining items—so the overall likelihood is the product of two CL components for each task, as summarised in Equation B4.

$$P_n([y_{\text{best}} = b, y_{\text{worst}} = w] | \alpha_n, t_1, t_2) = \frac{\exp(V_{nb}, t_1)}{\sum_{j=1}^J \exp(V_{nj}, t_1)} \times \frac{\exp(-V_{nw}, t_2)}{\sum_{j=1}^{J-1} \exp(-V_{nj}, t_2)} \quad (B4)$$

As we expect heterogeneity in priorities across stakeholders and mountain areas, we relax the homogeneity assumption by estimating a latent class model (LCM) (Boxall and Adamowicz 2002). In this specification,

the best–worst choice probabilities are conditioned on membership in class $s = 1, \dots, S$ while a multinomial logit allocation model assigns individuals to classes as a function of covariates z_n (e.g., value chain and regional features). The class-membership probabilities are specified according to Equation B5 with a log-scale parameter λ_w associated with worst choices. One parameter of the S vector is set to zero for identification.

$$h_{ns} = \frac{\exp(\lambda_w \gamma_s z_n)}{\sum_{s=1}^S \exp(\lambda_w \gamma_s z_n)} \quad (B5)$$

The unconditional probability of observing a stakeholder's full sequence of best–worst choices integrates over classes (Equation B6).

$$P_n(y_{\text{best}} = b, y_{\text{worst}} = w) = \sum_{s=1}^S h_{ns} P_{ni_s} \quad (B6)$$

We estimate parameters by maximum likelihood. The analyst sets the number of classes on the basis of information criteria alongside considerations of parsimony and interpretability (Swait 1994). For this study, a four-class solution was selected as the best compromise between model fit and parsimony, based on the diminishing returns exhibited by the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) and because of the clarity it affords for drawing policy-relevant insights. To provide further information about determinants of class membership, the final specification also included covariates related to the mountain value chain to which the stakeholder is linked (characteristics of the value chain, e.g., production type, resource use etc. and characteristics of the mountain area, e.g., location, altitude etc.). These covariates were first included separately and then alongside the other significant covariates, provided that they were not correlated. This process continued until only the significant covariates remained.

To facilitate interpretation, we transform the estimated coefficients into ratio-scaled 'impact scores', which express the predicted percentage of times the objective θ_{is} is chosen as best/worst within class s and the number of items J per choice task (Equation B7) and then rescale them to a 0–100 metric.

$$\text{Ratio-scaled impact score}_{is} = \frac{\exp(\theta_{is})}{(\exp(\theta_{is}) + J - 1)} \quad (B7)$$

Appendix C

Descriptive Statistics of the Sample

TABLE C1 | Descriptive statistics of the sample.

Variables	Ratio
General characteristics	
Age (25–40) (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	26.9
Age (40–65) (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	69.4
Age (> 65) (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	3.7
Woman (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	38.0
Education level: University degree (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	92.6
Covariates used in the latent class model	
Mediterranean: the value chain mainly lies within a Mediterranean mountain area (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	52.8
Protected Designation of Origin: the value chain is attached to this type of geographical indication (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	15.7
Organic: the value chain focuses on organic products (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	6.5
Animalp: the value chain relies on animal products (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	36.1
Permcrops: the value chain relates to permanent cropping (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	29.6
CultureHi: the respondent perceives that the value chain to which s/he is attached makes a strong contribution to local culture/ education (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	68.5
DiversifiHi: the respondent perceives that the value chain to which s/he is attached makes a strong impact on the diversification of income sources (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	70.4

FIGURE C1 | Sectors to which the surveyed stakeholders were attached (in % of respondents). *Note:* Some respondents specified attachment to more than one sector.

Appendix D

Choice and Modelling Information

TABLE D1 | Most-important and least-important choices within the best–worst scaling experiment.

Objective	Most important		Least important		Most minus least important
	#	%	#	%	
O1-Cooperation	128	16.9	68	9.0	60
O2-Human capital	105	13.9	93	12.3	12
O3-Sustainable use of local assets	140	18.5	68	9.0	72
O4-Inclusiveness	9	1.2	263	34.8	−254
O5-Adaptive capacity	98	13.0	97	12.8	1
O6-Ecological resilience	131	17.3	74	9.8	57
O7-Attractiveness & wellbeing	145	19.2	93	12.3	52
Total	756	100.0	756	100.0	

TABLE D2 | Goodness of fit statistics for different latent class model (LCM) solutions.

Model	LL	BIC	AIC	R ²	No. parameters
1-Class solution (MNL)	−1170.58	2373.93	2355.15	0.1063	7
2-Class solution	−1145.34	2356.24	2318.69	0.2269	14
3-Class solution	−1122.03	2342.39	2286.07	0.2969	21
4-Class solution	−1102.90	2336.90	2261.80	0.3289	28
5-Class solution	−1085.68	2335.24	2241.36	0.3593	35
6-Class solution	−1072.22	2341.10	2228.45	0.3636	42
7-Class solution	−1061.79	2353.00	2221.58	0.3802	49

Abbreviations: AIC, Akaike information criterion; BIC, Bayesian information criterion; LL, log-likelihood.

TABLE D3 | Multinomial logit model (MNL) and four-class latent class logit model (LCM) without covariates (reference = O4-Inclusiveness).

	Four-class LCM									
	MNL		Class 1		Class 2		Class 3		Class 4	
	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE
Membership probability	—		0.209		0.263		0.319		0.209	
Mean parameters										
O1-Cooperation	2.961***	0.338	3.246***	0.698	2.624***	0.529	3.328***	0.490	4.797***	1.379
O2-Human capital	2.659***	0.342	0.203	0.796	3.058***	0.525	2.838***	0.547	5.621***	1.394
O3-Sustainable use of local assets	3.050***	0.349	3.301***	0.818	1.769***	0.531	3.204***	0.514	6.670***	1.453
O5-Adaptive capacity	2.563***	0.342	3.522***	0.781	2.060***	0.551	2.417***	0.449	4.332***	1.339
O6-Ecological resilience	2.973***	0.349	2.994***	0.955	2.049***	0.594	2.362***	0.508	7.920***	1.467
O7-Attractiveness & well-being	2.949***	0.355	3.741***	0.895	3.925***	0.539	1.282***	0.483	5.736***	1.415
Class specific constant	—		−0.163	0.288	0.065	0.251	0.260	0.250	−0.163	0.250
Scale factor worst responses	−0.556***	0.149	−0.475***	0.145						
Goodness of fit										
LL	−1170.58		−1102.90							
AIC/N	1.038		0.997							
Observations (individuals)	2268 (108)		2268 (108)							

Note: ***, **, * denote significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively.